

Research

An Analysis of the Determinants of Investment Attractiveness for FDI Inflows into the Russian Federation

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Abstract: After the annexation of the Crimean Peninsula in March 2014, the US, the countries of the EU, and their partner countries imposed economic sanctions against the Russian Federation. Shortly thereafter President Putin introduced retaliatory sanctions. Along with the sanctions, came the oil price downturn that caused the outflow of Foreign Direct Investments (FDI). Thus, defining and studying the primary factors of investment attractiveness for the FDI inflow is the problem of the current importance. The following paper using theoretical and empirical methods is focusing on studying the main economic determinants of investment attractiveness for FDI inflows into the Russian Federation. The primary objective of this paper is to determine economic factors influencing the FDI inflows into Russia, focusing on the non-favorable economic and geopolitical conditions. Overall, it answers the question “What are the main current determinants of investment attractiveness for the foreign direct investments into the Russian economy?”.

The analysis of the structural dynamics of FDI inflows into the Russian Federation showed the main investor countries are offshore territories, which is not favouring the further development. Overall, the investment environment in Russia cannot be called generally attractive for the FDI due to the high level of corruption, unstable currency, and lack of developed infrastructure. The empirical part applies regression analysis of controlled variables. A correlation matrix shows that all the used variables are related correctly. Further, the author found that throughout the given time-frame (2010-2018) among all the economic determinants the most impact on the FDI inflows into the Russian Federation had GDP and the level of trade openness. However, against all expectations, economic sanctions did not have a significant impact on FDI inflows.

Keywords: Foreign Direct Investments, Determinants of Investment Attractiveness, the Russian Federation

1.Introduction

Throughout the history of the global economy and economic affairs, the welfare and business environment of the country have been depending heavily on the geopolitical situation. Thus, the political and economic orientation of one state can have an effect on the situation in another. On October 9th, 2014, Iran and Saudi Arabia decreased the prices of oil for the export contracts. As the economy of the Russian Federation heavily depends on the products of Fuel and Energy Complex (oil and gas), lower prices had a crucial impact on the economy. The revenues from oil production form a significant part of the Russian GDP (Gross Domestic Product). On August 5th, 2015 prices dropped down to 50,00 US dollars for the barrel (cont. 2012 year-average price was 111,63 US dollars per barrel; 53,49 US dollars per barrel on Dec. 22, 2018). Lower petrol prices led to inflation, which reached 7,8% in 2014 and 15,5% in 2015. Despite the decrease in the inflation rate (2,9% in 2018), the situation in the Russian market remains unstable for foreign investors.

Due to the social and economic sanctions, imposed by the United States of America and the European Union countries in March 2014 after the annexation of the Crimea peninsula, and the sanctions retaliation the import-export relations between a number of western countries and the Russian Federation were damaged. The negative effects of the imposed sanctions were observed in the financial sector of the economy. Russian banks and enterprises were put under a ban on lending activities in the western banks. According to PwC's data, in 2013 Russian emitters attracted 46.4 billion US dollars in the Eurobond market, while in 2015 it was only approximately 5 billion US dollars. Moreover, Russian companies with the state's capital share of more than 50% (Including two Russian petroleum giants PJSC Gazprom and PJSC Rosneft), lost the right to place their stocks in the European market. In addition to that, sanctions put a restriction on access to manufacturing technologies.

However, regardless of inflation and unstable currency, the Russian market remains attractive for a certain group of foreign investors. Under the conditions of economic instability, the attraction of Foreign Direct Investments (FDI) has become one of the most relevant directions for further economic development, as it is one of the most efficient tools for bringing foreign capital, innovations, and technologies. The FDI is aiming at long-term cooperation and, according to many economists and researchers, has a positive effect on the country's economy. The FDI, like

other forms of investments, is an economic concept that is influenced by macroeconomic factors. However, the inflow of FDI to a county is highly dependent on international politics.

Thus, the purpose of this paper is to analyze the leading factors of attractiveness for the FDI into the Russian Federation from 2010 to 2018 under the conditions of unfavorable political environment. The timing framework is based on the economic environment and the FDI dynamics four years before the sanctions and four years after. The lack of data does not make it possible to conduct research until recent times. The paper answers the question: *What are the main current determinants of investment attractiveness for foreign direct investments into the Russian economy?*

2. Literature review

Polusmakova (2013) studied the main obstacles for attracting FDI and its significance for the Russian economy. According to her study, among the problems that require urgent solutions the most important are: undeveloped economic and legal systems that would protect the interests of foreign investors. Yanuk and Yafizova (2015) to the problems described above added uneven geographical distribution of foreign investments, a high level of corruption, and the downfall of the Russian economy.

Golovina and Lungu (2015), Ponomareva (2015) gave an appraisal of foreign investors' activity in the Russian Federation.

The factors of investment attractiveness for this thesis study were determined through the results of Birnleitner (2014) survey. Throughout the survey economic factors, more specifically GDP, inflation rate, and openness of trade proved to be the most significant for the FDI inflow.

The main findings of the analyses, conducted on the development of the inflationary processes in the Russian Federation, showed that the main reasons of comparatively high inflation rate in Russia are federal budget's strong dependency on the export of the natural resources, increased tariffs of the natural monopolies, increased taxes, outflow of the investments, slowdown in economic growth and the most recent factors is the imposed economic factors (Vsyakikh & Bogdanova 2016). Banyak (2007) mentioned that among the countries with emerging economies, macroeconomics instability, and a high inflation rate, in particular, has a negative impact on the country's attractiveness for foreign investments.

A number of researches agreed that the imposition of economic sanctions had a crucial effect on the investment attractiveness of the Russian Federation and the policy of the cancellation of sanction should be implemented for the improvement of the investment environment of the country (Gorbunova 2018, Viderker & Durdieva 2016). Bubnova, Klinova (2017) mentioned that currently stagflation process can be observed in Russia.

Shmeleva, Bilinkina, Bikanova (2016) in their work defined main preconditions of the Russian ruble devaluation, including Winter Olympics in Sochi, the annexation of the Crimean Peninsula, and a sharp fall in oil prices.

According to Larchenko (2019) in the mid-term and long-term perspectives sanctions could lead to big challenges for development, due to the lack of advanced equipment and technologies for the realization of the projects on the arctic shelf.

Kachmazarova (2015) stated that the exchange value of the national currency could be one of the main factors of investment attractiveness in the case of Russia, as an exchange value is highly dependent on oil prices.

3. Methodology

The following research offers a theoretical and empirical analysis of the determinants of investment attractiveness for FDI into the Russian economy. Theoretical analysis was conducted through the complete review of the existing publications and researches dedicated to determinates influencing the FDI inflows into Russia including inflation rate, GDP and trade openness, the exchange value of the national currency, and economic sanctions imposed in 2014.

The empirical method, along with the method of sequential exclusion of insignificant variables is applied for estimating the factors that influence the investment inflow in the Russian Federation. The dependent variable is the net inflow of the FDI into the Russian Federation. Independent variables are defined as the determinants of investment attractiveness: inflation rate, GDP, trade openness, the exchange value of the ruble, price of Brent oil, and economic sanctions.

The data is obtained from reliable and authoritative sources including the World Bank database and database of the Central Bank of the Russian Federation.

4. Dynamics and sectoral structure of FDI in the Russian Federation

The value of the FDI in Russia has significantly decreased during the period of economic recession. The external «oil shock» that happened in 2014-2016, also had an effect on the investment inflow into the Russian Federation. The major investments in such industries as electrical energy and intercommunication led to the oversupply. However, the other economic sectors (except for the primary production) were lacking capital inflow, which complicated the possibility of overcoming the current economic stagnation.

The outflow of foreign capital from Russia started in 2014. After the imposition of economic sanctions, a number of big foreign enterprises had to stop their business activities. In the following years, this trend only became stronger, due to the drop in oil prices and deterioration of international relations. Table 1 introduces the structure and dynamics of the foreign direct investment inflow into the Russian Federation: flows by industry.

Table 1: Foreign Direct Investment in the Russian Federation: flows by Industry (million USD)

Economic activity/Year	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018
Total	43 167	55 084	50 588	69 219	22 031	6 853	32 539	28 557	8 785
Agriculture, Forestry and Fishing	318	236	231	619	-30	270	-141	-274	58
Mining and Quarrying	3 759	4 549	4 808	7 101	4 545	11 489	22 304	8 329	5 043
Manufacturing	9 843	8 348	6 385	16 494	1 173	6 839	4 884	2 867	4 289
Electricity, Gas, Steam and Air Conditioning	1 410	2 207	1 869	1 768	1 682	-1 940	-98	1 173	696
Water Supply: sewerage, waste	16	15	17	26	13	-20	-9	-37	-2

management and remediation activities									
Construction	394	3 771	3 928	2 895	2 718	-1 051	-342	2 072	-214
Wholesale and Retail Trade; Repair of Motor Vehicles and Motorcycles	5 480	18 096	13 241	20 542	3 240	3 996	1 701	1 826	-7075
Transportation and Storage	-176	1 153	-281	349	-743	-1 689	-72	369	-1 518
Accommodation and Food Service Activities	266	-140	150	187	93	112	79	74	-152
Information and Communication	3 317	1 574	-2 182	-1 292	-2 361	-6 514	-362	780	-1 197
Financial and Insurance Activities	7 661	9 338	14 983	14 456	7 842	-2 825	3 301	7 136	8 368
Real Estate Activities	3 197	2 478	1 984	1 728	-830	339	399	1 402	583
Professional, Scientific and Technical Activities	3 611	155	115	75	79	90	15	2 523	-4 107

Administrative and Support Service Activities	390	-357	-579	-422	83	-473	-179	-423	3 471
Public Administration and Defence; Compulsory Social Security	1	1	-1	0	0	0	0	0	-2
Education	-12	4	6	-1	5	2	2	16	4
Human Health and Social Work Activities	6	182	448	348	156	-84	-37	78	31
Arts, Entertainment and Recreation	341	10	385	30	142	-150	-39	43	-52
Other Service Activities	2 838	2 576	4 091	3 053	3 870	-2 345	634	0	12
<i>Unallocated</i>	506	887	990	1 264	353	806	500	603	549

(*Source:* The Central Bank of the Russian Federation, External Sector Statistic, 2019.)

Despite the unfavourable political situation, economic sanctions, and fall in oil prices, some sectors of the Russian economy are still receiving foreign investments. Foreign investors are mainly interested in the fundamental and most competitive industries (Golovina & Lungu, 2015). Thus, according to the Central Bank estimations, mining and quarrying, manufacturing, wholesale and retail trade, and financial and insurance activities received the most foreign investments under the conditions of economic sanctions. Moreover, the outflow of the capital did not surpass the inflows in the following industries. At the same time, in 2015, most of the economy's sectors were hit by the outflow of the foreign capital.

The analysis of foreign investment distribution by industries shows, that the key factors for selecting an industry for capital investments are access to the developed markets and available resources (Kachmazarova, 2015). The concentration of foreign capital in some particular sectors of the economy restrains the main reason for the growth of the other industries, thus, the introduction of the new technologies for attracting investments for the undeveloped sectors of the economy is required.

When studying the dynamics of foreign investments' inflow, it is vital to analyse the activity of the main countries investing in the Russian Federation. Table 2 is introducing the data on foreign direct investment in the Russian Federation: flows by the partner country.

Table 2: Foreign Direct Investment in the Russian Federation: Flows by Partner Country
(millions USD)

Year/Coun try	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018
Total	74 783	36 583	43 168	55 084	50 588	69 219	22 031	6 853	32 539	28 557	8 785
Bermuda Islands	9 959	2 243	436	594	-320	404	1 777	2 239	2 551	1 256	843
Britain Virgin Island	5 519	1 761	2 139	7 225	2 475	9 379	3 123	2 374	1 101	-827	1 223
China	-49	231	336	126	450	597	1 271	645	345	140	-13
Cyprus	20 428	4 182	12 287	12 999	1 985	8 266	3 158	-7 069	-436	8 674	-10 108
Finland	1 415	518	347	217	349	216	124	-272	253	50	582
France	604	696	2 592	1 107	1 232	2 121	2 224	1 686	1 997	854	1 134

Germany	3 379	2 914	3 196	2 234	2 265	335	349	1 48	224	470	341
								3			
Ireland	52	564	2 326	5 306	9 877	10 39	-531	623	-	889	-
						9			1 789		3 850
Japan	195	272	473	369	596	369	295	447	140	83	345
Luxembou rg	1 403	6 195	2 892	4 106	10 81	11 63	-693	-	-939	3 378	-506
					4	8		5 77			
								0			
Netherland s	10 18	-	3 733	7 383	10 33	5 716	1 102	-246	165	-	7 846
	4	3 391			0					1 427	
Norway	374	302	59	66	69	94	51	-93	34	31	44
Sweden	1 892	1 863	1 831	2 025	1 322	-	166	122	530	20	372
						1 203					
Switzerlan d	569	1 925	-1	741	401	1 086	2 472	203	1 842	1 511	1 690
the UK	1 007	699	1 142	2 007	46	18 92	120	1 11	478	2 076	2 522
						7		2			
the USA	2 161	2 296	435	276	285	485	708	209	402	495	376

(Source: The Central Bank of the Russian Federation, External Sector Statistic, 2019.)

According to Table 2, the main countries investing in the Russian economy from 2010 to 2018 are Cyprus, Luxembourg, Bermuda Islands, British Virgin Islands, the Netherlands, the UK, and Switzerland. Most of the countries above, in a varying degree, are used as an offshore country (Ponomareva, 2015). Thus, the main feature of the foreign investment inflow's structure by the partner country is the significant amount of offshore investments. The following foreign investments are not a very accurate indicator of the investment attractiveness of the Russian Federation — as a result of unfavourable conditions for conducting business activities, the

entrepreneurs register the organisations in offshore territories, and return the profits the organisations make, back into the Russian economy. It should be mentioned that the big part of the foreign investment inflow has arrived from the offshore territories, but officially it is considered as foreign investment. Thus, most of the foreign direct investment is external credits and loans, that are not aimed at the modernisation of the economy and capital funds (Yanuk & Yafizova, 2015).

Other major country partners are Luxembourg, the Netherlands, and the United Kingdom. Although the following countries are not offshore territories, they also are frequently used in the business activities of the Russian entrepreneurs. Due to the «transparent» legislation system and favourable legal framework, the entrepreneurs register special assignment companies in these European countries. The reason for the close economic relationship between Luxembourg and Russian is collateral project cooperation in such industries as energy development, metallurgy, automotive industry, finance, health care, technology, communications, and informational support.

The dynamics of the foreign direct investment inflow from the non-offshore countries throughout the last ten years had been very multidirectional. Under the condition of economic sanctions, the inflow of investment from the United States in 2015 decreased by 70% and in Switzerland by 92% compared with the previous year; however, the amount of the investment from Germany increased by 77% in 2015.

In general, the dynamics of the foreign investment into the Russian Federation shows a decrease of the investment inflow. The sectoral structure of the Foreign Direct Investment in the Russian Federation shows that the foreign investments mainly are concentrated in some particular sectors of the economy (mining and quarrying, manufacturing, wholesale and retail trade, financial and insurance activities). Geographically the Foreign Direct Investments are not distributed equally as well, most of the investments are concentrated in Moscow, the Moscow region, St. Petersburg and the Leningrad region.

5. An overview of the Determinants of Investment Attractiveness for the FDI into the Russian Economy

Inflation Rate

According to the findings of Banyak (2007), among the emerging economies, macroeconomics instability, and a high inflation rate, in particular, has a negative impact on the

country's attractiveness for foreign investments. Figure 1 provides data on inflation rate dynamics in the Russian Federation during the period from 2008 to 2018.

Figure 1. Dynamics of Inflation Rate in the Russian Federation (%)

(*Source:* World Bank, World Bank Open Data, 2019.)

Experts believe, that one of the main reasons for the high inflation rate in the Russian Federation is the state budget's strong dependency on the price of mineral resources on the international markets (Vsyakikh & Bogdanova, 2016).

Some experts suggest, that a stagflation process can be observed in Russia nowadays (Bubnova & Klinova 2017). The stagflation process can be described by the combination of several processes: economic slowdown and increase in price levels. Stagflation processes usually appear in the local economy under the conditions of the global economic crisis.

In general, the inflation rate in the Russian Federation is slowly decreasing, which could be a positive factor for attracting Foreign Direct Investments, but such negative factor as economic slowdown could become a serious obstacle for the inflow of foreign investment.

GDP

To minimize different types of risks foreign investors seek relatively developed and stable economies. The economic growth and economic potential of the country are directly related to the

increase in GDP. Figure 2 provides the data on changing dynamics of GDP in the Russian Federation.

Figure 2. GDP Dynamics in the Russian Federation from 2008 to 2018 (millions of US dollars)

(Source: The Central Bank of the Russian Federation, 2019.)

According to the Analytical Organization for the Government of the Russian Federation (2019), the GDP of the Russian Federation starting from 2013 to 2017 was steadily declining. In 2014 an economic growth has significantly decreased, due to the sharp drop in the energy and raw materials' prices and the loss of access to the foreign financial markets. In 2015 GDP in Russia continued to decline as a result of declining demand, consumption, and gross accumulation.

An increase in prices on oil in the second half of 2016 had a positive impact on GDP, as well as on the metal, coal, and natural gas; an export of engineering and metallurgical products; a defense complex was steadily growing. A negative impact on the GDP growth had a decline in consumer and investment demand.

The economy of the Russian Federation depends on many internal and external factors. Over 50% of the structure of the national budget is consisting of the revenues from hydrocarbon production. Thus, the oil and gas industry could be called extremely significant for the economic growth in Russia.

Figure 3. The Structure of GDP in the Russian Federation in 2014, 2017 and 2018 by the Production Account (share in %)

(Source: Analytical Organization for the Government of the Russian Federation, 2019.)

By 2018 the GDP in Russia increased by around 30%, mainly due to the relative growth of mining and manufacturing sectors of the economy. The domestic demand remains depressed, despite the certain appreciation of the national currency. The relative growth rates performed mining, manufacturing, and transportation and storage. The dynamics of the construction sector of the economy was not significantly changing over the following years, this is due to the fact that major construction projects were finished or suspended due to the economic sanctions. The Finance and Insurance sector remains stable due to the growth of the financial intermediation services and securities trust management, as the volume of the portfolio investments on the Russian capital market significantly increased (Figure 3).

Trade Openness

The degree of trade openness of the country is usually estimated with basic indexes of county's involvement in international trade, such as Export Quota (XQ)-the share of export (X) in Gross Domestic Product (GDP) of the country, %:

Equation 1:

$$XQ = \frac{X}{GDP} \times 100\%$$

When the value of export quota is less than 10%, the economy of the country is considered relatively closed; when the share of export is more than 35%, the economy is considered relatively open.

Another important indicator is Import Quota (MQ)-the share of import (M) in GDP of the country, %:

Equation 2:

$$MQ = \frac{M}{GDP} \times 100\%$$

The increase in import quota means the growth of openness of the economy of the country, but it might not be a positive characteristic of the country's economy, because the high share of imports could indicate an economy's high dependence on foreign supply.

Foreign Trade Quota (FTQ)-Foreign Trade Turnover (FTT)—an aggregated volume of export (X) and import (M)—to GDP ratio, %:

Equation 3:

$$FTQ = \frac{FTT}{GDP} \times 100\%$$

Foreign Trade Turnover has a stimulating or inhibitory effect on the national economy when it reaches the level of 25% of the GDP. According to other estimations, the economy is considered as closed when FTQ is less than 27%.

Table 3: GDP, Export and Import of the Russian Federation from 2008 to 2018

Year\Index (millions USD)	GDP, millions USD	Export, millions USD	Export Quota, %	Import, millions USD	Import Quota, %	Foreign Trade Turnover, million USD	Foreign Trade Quota, %
2010	1 524 900	392 674	25,8 %	245 680	16,1 %	638 354	41,9 %
2011	2 051 600	515 409	25,2 %	318 555	15,6 %	833 964	40,7 %

2012	2 210 200	527 434	23,9 %	335 771	15,2 %	863 205	39,1 %
2013	2 297 100	521 835	22,7 %	341 269	14,9 %	863 104	37,6 %
2014	2 063 600	496 806	24,1 %	307 875	14,1 %	804 681	38,1 %
2015	1 365 800	341 419	24,1 %	193 021	14,1 %	534 440	39,1 %
2016	1 283 100	281 709	21,1 %	191 494	14,1 %	473 203	36,9 %
2017	1 278 000	353 102	27,6 %	238 384	18,7 %	591 486	46,3 %
2018	1 658 000	443 130	26,7 %	248 701	15 %	691 831	41,7 %

(*Source:* Central Bank of the Russian Federation, 2019.)

The analysis of the trade indicators of the Russian Federation shows, that the level of trade and economic openness remains relatively high in recent years comparing to the years of the economic slowdown in 2009 and in 2015, but relatively low compared to other countries.

According to the Global Economy database (2017), the average level of trade openness was 90,55% in 2017, with the highest value of 412,97% in Luxembourg, and the lowest in Sudan with a value of 22,5%.

Exchange Value of Ruble and Oil Price

One other not obvious economic factor that has an impact on the investment attractiveness of Russia is the devaluation of the Russian ruble, that started in the middle of 2013 and reached its peak in January 2016. The economists outline a number of ruble devaluation's preconditions. Firstly, the 2014 Winter Olympics in Sochi required large financial investments. Secondly, the annexation of the Crimean Peninsula was followed by significant expenses, used for the full political, economic, and legal integration. Thirdly, sharp fall in oil prices (Shmeleva & Bilinkina & Bikanova, 2016).

In 2014 the Central Bank introduced a floating rate of exchange. The floating rate of exchange is a required measure for the inflation targeting regime, which is applied for ensuring the stability of the prices. In the second part of 2014, the dynamics of the national currency's exchange rate were under the influence of different factors: geopolitical environment, economic sanctions, and drop in oil prices in the global market. Figure 4 offers an interactive dynamic

between the Russian ruble exchange rate and Brent oil prices. The figure clearly describes the sharp drop in oil prices at the end of 2014 was followed by a significant decrease in the ruble's value at the beginning of 2015. The same happened in the first quarter of 2016 when the price of oil decreased by 36,77 US dollars per barrel and the value of ruble fell to 74,63 rubles for 1 US dollar. The connection between the ruble's exchange rate and the oil price cannot be called direct, however, under the conditions of economic recession or crisis Russian government ties the exchange rate of the ruble to the global prices on energy resources, making the economy dependent on the oil and gas manufacturing.

Figure 4. The Interaction between the Exchange of the Russian Ruble and Price of Brent Oil from 2010 to 2018

(Source: Central Bank of the Russian Federation, 2019.)

Another major factor that influences the development of the Russian economy is the declining price of oil. In 2014, 51% of the revenue of the Federal Budget consisted of oil and gas revenues, in 2018 this number changed to 46%. Certainly, even the small fall in oil prices has a big impact on the economy that is heavily dependent on the export of oil and gas.

Over the last years, the main obstacles for the development of the oil and gas industries were a drop in oil prices and economic sanctions. Due to the imposition of sanctions “Shell” had to stop its activity in Russia; “Total S.A” transferred the share in the Bazhenov Formation (West Siberian basin) to “Lukoil”, the share in Shtokman field (South Barents Basin) to “Gazprom”. Thus, the sanctions had an impact on the most vulnerable part of the oil and gas industry — access to the technologies, services, and innovations. The development of the oil and gas industry requires technological cooperation with the countries that have an innovative capacity. However, the imposed sanctions put such cooperation under restrictions, and consequently the change of the priorities in international energy policy.

Thus, the main issues that delay the development of oil industry are sanction, lack of innovations and modern technologies that are necessary for the extraction of the hardly accessible resources, the drop in the price of raw hydrocarbons, which causes the lack of investment into the oil and gas production and geological exploration.

Economic Sanctions

In 2014, after the annexation of the Crimean Peninsula and the conflict in western Ukraine, a number of countries started imposing sanctions against the Russian Federation. The initiator of the sanctions was the United States of America, later joined the European Union countries, G7 countries, and other countries partners of the US and the EU.

The imposition of sanctions, certainly, had an indirect impact on the economies of both sides. However, sanctions directly affected a decrease in GDP in the Russian Federation. The trade restriction between the countries led to an increase in expenses on the search of new suppliers, the search for new substitutes-goods, and the reorganization of domestic manufacturing (Viderker & Durdieva, 2016).

In 2014, president V. Putin signed an executive order, which limits import of the certain types of agricultural goods, foodstuffs, and raw materials from the countries that imposed economic sanctions against Russia.

According to different estimations, the losses from the imposed sanctions are approximately 140 billion US dollars. However, in reality, this number can be larger, as at the same time with the imposition of sanctions in the Russian Federation happened the events favoring the increase in financial losses, including annual capital outflow, the restriction of access to the

external credit recourses, the contraction of revenues from sales of raw hydrocarbons, declining number of foreign assets, drop in people's income and outflow of deposits from private investors.

6. Analysis of the Determinants of Investment Attractiveness for FDI into the Russian Economy

Data collection

The secondary data has been a key attribute in this paper. The secondary data is usually published with different intentions and in consequence, it was used with the utmost care. The data from reliable sources including World Bank database, the database of the Central Bank of the Russian Federation, International Monetary Fund database, Ministries of Trade and Finance, along with raw data and compiled data such as annual reports, books, and articles published by the consulting and advisory companies on the situation on the Russian market were used in this research paper.

Research method and research approach

The variables for the model were chosen according to the research paper «Attractiveness of Countries for Foreign Direct Investments from the Macro-Economic Perspective» by H. Birnleitner (2014). Such factors as exchange rate, price of oil, and economic sanctions are not mentioned as the main determinants of the country's investment attractiveness in academic researches, these are vital in the case of the Russian Federation. Economic sanctions imposed in 2014 were used as dummy variables.

The time frame (2010-2018) was chosen due to the date of the sanction imposition. Earlier data could lead to insignificant results and structural shifts, as in 1998 and 2008 happened two major financial crises affected foreign investment inflows.

The following paper applies the multilinear regression analysis of the dependent and controlled variables. The dependent and independent variables used for the statistical analysis of the paper are the following:

Y (*invest*) — the Foreign Direct Investment inflow into the Russian Federation, (billion US dollar);

X1 (*inf*) — inflation rate in the Russian Federation (percentage);

X2 (*gdp*) — GDP (billion US dollars);

X3 (*price*) — brent price (the price of Brent oil, US dollar);

X4 (*rate*) — exchange rate (US dollar to Russian ruble ratio);

X5 (*trade*) — trade openness (percentage);

X6 (*sanctions*) —economic sanctions (0=before sanctions; 1=after sanctions).

Results and Data interpretation

To define what determinants that have the most impact on the FDI inflow into the Russian Federation the following model is suggested:

Equation 4:

$$\ln invest = \ln gdp + \ln trade + \ln rate + \ln price + sanction$$

Including variables described in paragraph 4.2. The variable selection and descriptive statistic are offered in Model 1.

Model 1: Variables and descriptive statistic

	Variable	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
Dependent	invest	9.018	1.119	4.159	10.60
	gdp	6.067	0.233	5.529	6.430
	trade	3.689	0.0676	3.608	3.835
Independent	sanctions	0.543	0.505	0	1
	rate	3.748	0.345	3.332	4.313
	price	4.339	0.362	3.605	4.809

(Author's Calculation using Stata.)

For the better data interpretation, it is necessary to build a correlation model to understand how the most significant variables are related.

Model 2: Correlation analysis

	invest	gdp	trade	sanctions	rate	price
invest	1					
gdp	0.567	1				
trade	0.067	-0.181	1			
sanctions	0.368	-0.560	0.0789	1		
rate	-0.490	-0.739	0.108	0.878	1	
price	0.573	0.830	-0.120	-0.719	-0.879	1

(Author's Calculation using Stata.)

The model above shows the correlation coefficients between the variables. The correlation coefficients between GDP and oil price, and foreign investment are relatively large — 0.567 and 0.067, respectively. This indicates a greater relation between oil price and GDP and the investment inflow, which proves the dependency of the Russian economy on the products of oil and gas complex. The exchange rate of the Russian ruble against the US dollar negatively correlated with the investment inflow. With the rise of the exchange rate the Russian ruble has depreciated, therefore, foreign goods and services have become more expensive compared to the domestic ones, which reduces the amount of the overseas investments; the correlation coefficient is — 0,490. Finally, the degree of opening up also has a positive impact on investment, but the correlation coefficient is relatively small — 0.067.

To determine the main economic factors influencing the inflow of FDI into the Russian Federation was conducted regression analysis.

First, the data were tested for multicollinearity, with a maximum value of 8.66 and a minimum value of 1.08. According to the test criteria, there is no multicollinearity between those variables. However, heteroscedasticity test results showed the existence of heteroscedasticity is

the data structure. In order to eliminate the deviation caused by heteroscedasticity, it was decided to conduct logarithmic adjustment on dependent and independent variables: *invest*, *trade*, *gdp* and *rate*. Since in the following research, *sanctions* are represented as dummy variables, the original values are selected for the regression.

Model 3: Multicollinearity test

Variable	VIF	1/VIF
rate	8.66	0.115418
price	6.30	0.158715
sanctions	3.86	0.259330
gdp	3.40	0.293702
trade	1.08	0.928428
Mean VIF	4.66	

(Author's Calculation using Stata.)

Model 4 introduces the results of the regression analysis. In the first column, only *gdp* is selected as the explanatory variable. The coefficient is positive and passes the significance test at the 1% level. In the second column, the degree of openness to trade is added. The variable *gdp* is still significantly positive, and the coefficient is slightly increased. This shows that *gdp* is one of the important factors affecting investment.

The next step is adding sanctions to the control variables. The impact of *gdp* and *trade* on investment inflow has not changed significantly. When all the other conditions remain, for every 1% increase in *gdp*, investment increases by 2.647%, and for every 1% decrease in *trade*, investment decreases by 2.594%. In the fourth and fifth columns, *rate* and *price* are added respectively. At this time, the significance of *gdp* decreases, and it is significant at 10% level of significance, also the coefficient decreases. This indicates that *invest* is affected by many factors, among which *gdp* has the largest impact. Overall, the sign of the coefficients for each variable appeared as expected.

Model 4: The results of the regression analysis

VARIABLES	lninvest				
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)
lngdp	2.661*** (0.731)	2.785*** (0.740)	2.647*** (0.940)	2.095* (1.113)	1.409 (1.470)
Intrade		2.561 (2.471)	2.594 (2.519)	2.371 (2.537)	2.571 (2.576)
sanctions			-0.108 (0.440)	0.550 (0.832)	0.334 (0.891)
Inrate				-1.296 (1.390)	-0.288 (1.977)
Inprice					1.123 (1.551)
Constant	-7.146 (4.443)	-17.36 (10.81)	-16.59 (11.43)	-7.901 (14.77)	-13.02 (16.51)
R-squared	0.321	0.347	0.349	0.371	0.384

*** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

(Author's Calculation using Stata, standard errors are in the parentheses.)

The combined results of the regression analysis show that among all the economic determinants of investment attractiveness the most influence on the FDI inflow into the Russian Federation have GDP and trade openness, whereas, economic sanctions do not have an expected impact on the investment inflow. Therefore, it could be recommended to the public authorities to increase the measures on creating a more favorable geopolitical image of the state and conditions for the foreign investors including simplification of the investment process, faster retraction of the economic sanctions, etc.

Conclusion

This paper has been studied the research question: “*What are the main determinants of investment attractiveness for foreign direct investments into the Russian economy?*” Studying this questing required a review of both, existing literature on the determinants of investment attractiveness and the dynamics of foreign investments in the Russian Federation, as well as economic indicators. Within the reviewed literature were analyzed:

1. FDI inflows into the Russian Federation, including an overview of the structure and dynamics of the foreign investments in the Russian Federation;
2. Main factors of investment attractiveness for FDI into the Russian Federation including inflation rate, trade openness, GDP, Exchange value of the ruble, price of oil and economic sanctions;
3. Statistical analysis of the determinants of investment attractiveness in the Russian Federation.

The volume of the FDI inflows into the Russian Federation has significantly decreased during the period of economic recession and economic sanctions. The external «oil shock» that happened in 2014-2016, also had an effect on the investment inflow into the Russian Federation.

According to the Central Bank, the main countries investing in the Russian economy from 2010 to 2018 were: Cyprus, Luxembourg, Bermuda Islands, British Virgin Islands, the Netherlands, the UK, and Switzerland. Most of the countries above, in a varying degree, are used as offshore territories.

Foreign investors primarily invest in the fundamental and most competitive industries. Thus, according to the Central Bank estimations, mining and quarrying, manufacturing, wholesale

and retail trade, and financial and insurance activities received the most foreign investments even under the conditions of economic sanctions.

On the point of main factors of investment attractiveness, the inflation rate in the Russian Federation is slowly decreasing, which can be a positive factor for attracting foreign direct investments; trade openness remains stable within the last ten years. Additionally, such factors as economic sanctions, exchange rate and fall in oil prices are not mentioned in academic researches on determinants of investment attractiveness, however, they are vital in case of Russia, due to instability of the Russian national currency and high dependency of the Russian economy on the export of the products of oil and gas sector.

The empirical analysis applied the regression model of the controlled variables. The first step — correlation matrix showed that the correlation coefficients between GDP and oil price, and foreign investment are relatively large — 0.567 and 0.067, respectively, which indicates greater relation between oil price and GDP and the investment inflow. Then, the data were tested for multicollinearity, with a maximum value of 8.66 and a minimum value of 1.08, consequently, no multicollinearity accrued between the tested variables. However, heteroscedasticity test results showed the existence of heteroscedasticity in the data structure. In order to eliminate the deviation caused by heteroscedasticity, it was decided to conduct logarithmic adjustment on the tested variables.

The results of the final experiment showed that among all the main determinants described in the following thesis research during the given period of time the most impact on the FDI inflow into the Russian Federation had trade openness and GDP. The price of Brent oil, the unstable exchange value of the national currency, and economic sanctions did not have a significant influence on the investment inflow.

Despite the results of the statistical model, the author of the following research paper considers the unfavorable geopolitical situation and technological inferiority as the main obstacles for economic growth and foreign investment inflow. Thus, the government should consider developing a long-term program for improving the international image of the Russian Federation, as well as consider the faster cancellation of economic sanctions.

References

- Birnleitner H., Attractiveness of Countries for Foreign Direct Investments from the Macro-Economic Perspective[J]. Symposium for Young Researchers, 2014, pp. 29-40.*
- Bubnova E., Klinova S., The Analysis and Appraisal of Inflationary Processes in the Modern Economic sciences and modern management issues, No.5, 2017, pp.45-54.*
- Golovina O., Lungu N., Investment Attractiveness of the Russian Economy in the Global Market[J]. Udmurt State University, 2015.*
- Gorbunova O., Attracting Foreign Direct Investment in the Russian Economy under the Sanctions[J]. The Financial University under the Government of the Russian Federation, Moscow, No.8, 2018.*
- Kachmazarova A., A Challenge of Attracting a Foreign Direct Investment in Russia[J]. International Scientific Research Journal, No 11, 2015, pp.49-50.*
- Larchenko L., Oil and Gas Industry under the Conditions of Uncertainty[J]. Society, Environment, Development. No.1, 2019, pp. 9-13.*
- Polusmakova V., Key Problems and Solutions of Attracting Foreign Direct Investment in Russia[J]. Herald of Volgograd State University, No.11, 2013, pp.39-42.*
- Ponomareva I., Foreign Investments in the Russian Economy: Dynamics, Analysis, Issues[J]. Postdoctoral Researcher, No.12, 2014, pp.169-174.*
- Shmeleva E., Bilinkina A., Bikanova O., The Impact of the National Currency's Exchange Rate of the Financial Market[J]. Issues of Economics and Management, No.3, 2016, pp.5-8.*
- Viderker N., Durdieva D., The Impact of the Sanctions on the Russian Banking Sector[J]. Herald of North Caucasus Federal University, No.5 (56), 2016, pp.45-49.*
- Vsyakikh Y., Bogdanova Y., Inflation in Russia: Dynamic, Managing Paths and the Factors of Risks[J]. The symbol of science, No.12-1, 2016, pp.1-7.*
- Yanuk E., Yafizova A., Problems of Attracting Foreign Investments in the Russian Economy[J]. Issues of Economics and Management, No.2, 2015, p.144.*
- https://www.cbr.ru/eng/statistics/macro_itm/sys/ (The Central Bank of the Russian Federation; External Sector Statistics; Database; Reference Date: September, 2019)*
- <https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/FP.CPI.TOTL.ZG?end=2018&locations=RU&start=2008> (The World Bank; World Bank Open Data; Database; Reference Date: September, 2019)*

https://www.cbr.ru/Reception/Faq/dofr_q_2/ (The Central Bank of the Russian Federation, Russian ruble exchange rate; Definition and Sources; Reference Date: November, 2019)

http://www.cbr.ru/eng/currency_base/dynamics/ (The Central Bank of the Russian Federation; External Sector Statistics; Database; Reference date: December 2019)

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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

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